

ANALYSIS OF TERMS ON LANGUAGE DIDACTICS ACCORDING TO THEIR LEXICO-SEMANTIC STRUCTURE

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Abstract: The article deals with the characterization of terminological units from the aspects of lexico-semantic structures which are specific for all their semantic features by means of linguistic approaches. The main semantic properties of terminological units of language didactics can be studied by means of linguistic analysis. The criteria could be defined as following: 1) terms which are formed by lexico-semantic ways; 2) polysemantic terms; 3) terms synonyms; 4) terms antonyms.

Keywords:

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Semantic changes in the formation of terms owing to their polysemantic features and relationships of meanings which may be found through the context. The main processes of formation and dynamic development of the terminological system of this science have been investigated owing to materials of English, Russian and Uzbek languages. However, it is important to define the role of national context in the development of the terminology system of language didactics by help of cross-cultural analysis, existing problems of comparative study of terminology, and searching corresponding equivalents of terms in Russian and Uzbek languages.

Semantic development of a term improves general meaning belonging to a term and changes according to its forms. However, sphere functioning of a term which connects with constantly developing scientific opinions for improving notions in the field of linguistics.

Among the terms there are number of absolute synonyms, as is known that it is possible to remove doubling in the subsystem or by the way of semantic differentiation for the nomination of new conceptions. Differentiation of synonymic microsystem as opposite process of fusing separate terminological microsystem, so another microsystem which serves for determinization of developing special vocabulary in all its historical sections. As a result of it there occurs the fusion of lexico-semantic variants of a single term, introduced in the integrating subsystem, but another subsystem which combines all similarity features of components of the lexical unit, transfers into polysemantic lexical unit.

The aim of the research is to improve the necessity of defining the main factors and sources of the formation and dynamic development terminological units of this science and their usage in the different socio-cultural contexts, including specific features and differences in the expansion of terms of the language didactics according corresponding culture.

Key words: lexico-semantic structures of terms, polysemy, polysemantic terms, terms synonym, terms antonyms, terms homonyms, language didactics, formation of terms, shift of meaning, classification of terms.

Terminological units in the field of linguistics make up the rapidly changing and active layer of the lexicon of the languages being compared. The composition of the terminological system of this field is regularly changing and updating due to the creation and introduction of new terms, as well as the emergence of proprietary terms. Therefore, conducting research related to the scientific study of the problems of interpretation of linguistic and socio-cultural features of linguistic and educational terminology is one of the urgent issues before linguists and terminological scientists.

When it comes to the classification of terms related to linguistics according to their lexical-semantic structure, basically all semantic features characteristic of them are studied from a linguistic point of view. Classification principles are determined as follows: 1) terms formed on the basis of the lexical-semantic method; 2) polysemantic terms; 3) term-synonyms; 4) term-antonyms.

According to our observations, in the terminology of linguistics, terms made from common words using the lexical-semantic method are of special importance. Such terms do not differ in form from common words, but their use as terms of this field has become a tradition. By studying the semantic structure of these terms, it is possible to more fully understand their features that differ from common words. Such features are visible in the interrelationship of the terminological lexicon with the lexicon in general use. It is in this connection that the process of termination in the terminological system of the universal lexicon is observed. In fact, due to the fact that common words perform the function of a term in a certain field, the scope of their task is expanded. Therefore, in this process, the words that perform the function of the term differ in a certain aspect from the meaning of the word in general use, and have an effective effect on the enrichment of the terminology system of each language.

It seems that the enrichment of the terminological lexicon takes place on the basis of the laws of the literary language. In particular, the creation of a term by the lexical-semantic method corresponds to the calculation of the lexicon in general use in a certain sense. The Russian linguist V.V. Vinogradov expresses the following opinion about this: "any science begins with the results achieved by the people's

thinking and speech, and does not separate from the people's language in the process of further development" [Vinogradov V.V., 1977; 165].

In our research, we come across some controversial points in the process of analyzing the meaning structure of the terms of linguistics from common words using the lexical–semantic method from a linguistic point of view. In particular, the question arises as to whether the terms of this field, made from commonly used words, have the characteristics of polysemy, synonymy, opposite meaning (antonym) or not. Based on the analysis of the studies carried out so far, it is worth noting that it seems to be true that this absolute concept in terminology that “any term must mean one thing” has a relative character in our eyes. First of all, every word is monosemantic (unambiguous) according to its appearance. In the process of gradual development, it has become a tradition in the language to use a lexical unit that is the name of an object to name a new object or phenomenon. In the end, this name serves as the name of another object. In this way, the second nomination appears. In particular, this situation is evident in the transition of word–noun to term–noun in the course of our research. The lexical meaning of the word develops through name transfer. In this case, the word used as the term – is assigned a functional meaning. This phenomenon is also called functional transfer in linguistics. Thus, since functional transfer is based on similarity, metaphorical transfer is based on some random signs between two things and the similarity of these signs, while functional transfer is based on similarity in terms of tasks. We can see this phenomenon in the following examples: jigsaw activities – type of exercise related to students’ exchange of information in the form of mixed construction, composite (mosaic). All variants of this type of exercises are referred to students in different forms of certain information. In this case, the full text form of the information is recommended to one of the applicants, and fragments of this text (a list of words or phrases, a set of questions, some opinions) are recommended to others. Accordingly, students will proceed with the following task. Relying on various fragments of this text, some missing information is asked from the student who has the full text form of the information, and on this basis, they begin to create an analogy related to the text.

The boomerang method is widely used in teaching foreign languages. In fact, this word “boomerang” means the name of “a sickle-shaped weapon”. This firearm is used as a defensive tool by the aborigines of the Australian continent, i.e. the indigenous people; jumbling – a confused mixture or heap; a muddle – a type of exercise encouraging to deliberately confuse the arrangement or classification of speech units, etc.

It was found that the phenomenon of polysemy, mentioned above, is also characteristic of the terms of this field. It is known that the emergence of another lexical meaning on the basis of one lexical meaning is the phenomenon of lexical

polysemy or homonymy. Accordingly, the amount of meaning can change in lexical polysemy. Studying the development of meaning in a polysemantic lexeme by the method of semitic analysis allows to visualize this process more clearly. We see such an approach in the example of the lexeme key – калит – key.

In English: the main lexical meaning of key lexeme is as follows: an instrument, usually of metal, for moving the bolt of a lock and thus locking or unlocking something; In Uzbek: key is defined as a metal tool used to open or close a lock. The second lexical meaning of this lexeme is manifested by acquiring a terminological meaning related to this field in such connections as lists of correct answers to test tasks. Although the concept of “subject” is preserved, the concept of “concrete thing” is replaced by the concept of “abstract thing”. So, the lexical meaning moves from concrete to abstract. As a result, the “metal tool” scheme is replaced by the “table showing the most correct answers to the test questions” scheme. Thus, the lexeme key in the English language has its own terminological meaning, which differs sharply from more than ten other lexical meanings related to it. The terminological lexeme related to this field of linguistics is included in the special dictionary co-authored by English terminologists J.Richards and R.Schmidt is defined as follows: key (in testing) a correct option or answer in a multiple – choice item. In fact, the alternatives of the English lexeme key in our study, such as the Uzbek key, are lexemes created by the method of semantic mapping.

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